
Digital Access and Resources in Traditional Medicine: A Content Analysis of AYUSH Research Councils and National Library Websites

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Abstract

The study analyses library websites of AYUSH research councils and national institutes in India under the Ministry of AYUSH. It examines these institutions' digital initiatives and resources, focusing on general information, resources, services, features, and accessibility. The study finds significant variations in information availability among institutes, with some providing comprehensive features like user manuals and feedback mechanisms, while others, like CCRAS and CCRYN, provide minimal information. The study emphasises the need for coordinated efforts to improve the quality and user-friendliness of AYUSH Institute library websites.

Keywords

AYUSH; Traditional Medicine; Research Councils;
National Institutes; Library Websites

Electronic access

The journal is available at www.jalis.in
DOI: **10.5281/zenodo.15193129**

Journal of Advances in Library and Information Science
ISSN: 2277-2219 Vol. 14. No.2. 2025. pp.108-116

1. INTRODUCTION

Digital technology has transformed information transmission, leading libraries to shift from traditional print-based archives to dynamic online platforms. In this digital age, library websites act as crucial gateways to knowledge, connecting users to many materials, services, and tools. The AYUSH (Ayurveda, Yoga, Naturopathy, Unani, Siddha, and Homoeopathy) systems play an important role in alternative and complementary medicine technologies, contributing to holistic healthcare practices around the world (*Digital Library / Ayush Next*, n.d.) (Shankar & Patwardhan, 2017). The research councils and national institutions under the Ministry of AUSH (MoA) play an important role in developing and promoting traditional medicine in India. Outlines the MoA's digital projects, including the AYUSH hospital management information system (A-HMIS) and the Traditional Knowledge Digital Library (TKDL) (*TKDL Traditional Knowledge Digital Library*, n.d.), which are crucial in cultivating the value of research and education in AYUSH systems (Muthappan et al., 2022) highlights the “Central Council for Research in Ayurvedic Sciences” (CCRAS) and its efforts in drug development, following scientific guidelines and ethical practices, to produce validated medicines for various diseases (Khanduri et al., 2018). Emphasizes the government's commitment to Ayurveda through policy creation and program execution to integrate it into the health system and promote it globally (Badiyani & Kotadia, 2023).

Interestingly, despite revealing that less than 30% of Indian households use traditional medical systems, it also underlines the tremendous faith in AYUSH as the key basis for its use (Srinivasan & Sugumar, 2017). This shows that, despite decreasing utilisation, there is a strong belief in the efficacy of AYUSH methods. Furthermore, a significant rise in the financial allocation for the MoA demonstrates the government's commitment to expanding the AYUSH industry (Gopal et al., 2023). The MoA has established research councils and national institutes that are vigorously involved in scientific research, drug development, and policy formulation to support and promote traditional AYUSH systems (Samal, 2015). The government has prioritized the integration of these systems into public health and expanding their global reach. AYUSH Research Councils and National Institutions play crucial roles in advancing research, teaching, and practice in their respective fields. Their library websites are essential resources for academics, scholars, practitioners, and

students, offering a wealth of information including scholarly articles, research findings, teaching materials, and therapeutic guidelines. However, these digital repositories' effectiveness and usefulness depend heavily on their design, content, accessibility, and user-friendliness (Rastogi et al., 2021).

2. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

The content analysis of library websites has been a widely explored subject, with studies examining their evolution, usability, and adherence to design standards. Aharony (2012) conducted a decade-long comparative analysis of academic library websites, highlighting the increased integration of e-journals, Web 2.0 applications, and user-centric design (Aharony, 2012). Similarly, Wilson (2015) evaluated Alabama academic library websites, noting a blend of online services but a lack of adherence to web accessibility standards (Wilson, 2015). Oyedokun et al. (2021) emphasized the balance between content quality and aesthetics, finding that Southwest Nigerian university libraries prioritize design over substance (Oyedokun et al., 2021). While some studies showcase advancements, others reveal gaps in accessibility and usability. Research indicates that many academic library websites fail to meet WCAG 2.1 accessibility standards, with GCC countries needing more millennial-friendly designs (Tiurkedzhy et al., 2022). Yesmin (2019) found that private university libraries in Bangladesh are more advanced in web resource integration than their public counterparts (Yesmin, 2019). Additionally, Yoon and Schultz (2017) observed the growing significance of research data management services, though their adoption varies widely (Yoon & Schultz, 2017).

Social media plays a crucial role in academic and public library engagement. Al-Daihani and AlAwadhi (2015) found that academic libraries use Twitter primarily for news, service promotion, and collection updates (Al-Daihani & AlAwadhi, 2015). Joo et al. (2020) noted that public libraries leverage social media to boost community engagement through events and announcements (Joo et al., 2020). Furthermore, libraries are increasingly incorporating diversity, equity, and inclusion (DEI) statements, though their scope and approach vary significantly (Ely, 2021). In the AYUSH domain, digital integration has gained momentum. The Ayush Grid (AG), launched in 2018 by the Ministry of AYUSH, aligns with India's national digital health infrastructure, supporting health services, education,

research, and citizen engagement (Ram, 2023). This development underscores the growing role of library websites in not only disseminating information but also fostering research and community interaction in traditional medicine.

3. SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

This study evaluates the library websites of AYUSH Research Councils and National Institutes, analyzing their content, accessibility, and user-friendliness. By assessing these digital platforms, it identifies their strengths, weaknesses, and areas for improvement. The findings will help enhance AYUSH library websites, ensuring they better support research, education, and practice in alternative medicine.

4. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The objectives of this study are mentioned below.

- To assess the comprehensiveness of information provided on AYUSH library websites.
- To Analyze Accessibility Features: Identify features that cater to users with diverse needs.
- To Compare and Contrast Websites: Conduct a comparative analysis of library websites across different AYUSH institutes. Identifying variations in content coverage and functionality.
- To highlight the strengths and weaknesses of individual websites.

5. METHODOLOGY

The research examines the digital initiatives and resources available on the websites of various AYUSH institutions, focusing on aspects such as general information, resources and services, features, and accessibility. Through a systematic content analysis, the study evaluates the extent to which these websites provide essential information and support for researchers, scholars, and the broader AYUSH community. The study's content was divided into two categories: 'Available' (A) and 'Not Available'. A mark of was given for 'Available' and for 'Not Available' (= **Available** = **Not Available**) (Rahman & Batcha, 2020). The collected data was given in tabular form and calculated to rank the Institute library website.

6. SCOPE AND LIMITATIONS

This study examines the content and functionality of library websites affiliated with AYUSH Research Councils and National Institutes in India. Covering 17 National Institutes and Research Councils under the AYUSH Ministry, the analysis focuses on key aspects such as library information (mission, vision, and introduction), user-centric details (hours, rules, and membership), and available resources (collections, infrastructure, e-journals, and databases). Additionally, it evaluates user-friendly features like OPAC, FAQs, User Manuals, and Ask a Librarian, as well as website functionalities, including updates, navigation, and login/registration. However, the study is limited to data available on library websites and does not assess physical facilities, resource quality, or user experiences. Findings rely solely on the accuracy of online information, which may be incomplete or outdated. Furthermore, website performance, mobile responsiveness, and accessibility features are not considered. This research is restricted to AYUSH library websites and does not include comparisons

with other academic or research libraries in India or globally.

7. AYUSH- RESEARCH COUNCILS AND NATIONAL INSTITUTES

The Ministry of AYUSH (Ayurveda, Yoga & Naturopathy, Unani, Siddha and Homeopathy), Government of India, is responsible for promoting and coordinating research in these traditional systems of medicine. There are two main categories of organisations under the AYUSH ministry.

- **Research Councils-05:** The Research Councils are apex bodies that formulate, coordinate, and promote scientific research in their respective systems of medicine. They are fully financed by the Government of India
- **National Institutes-12:** The National Institutes are premier institutions that conduct research, provide education and training, and deliver healthcare services in their respective systems of medicine.

Table-1:List of Research Councils and National Institute

Sl. No.	Name of the Institute	Abbreviations of Institute	Establishment Year	URL
1	"Institute of Teaching and Research in Ayurveda, Jamnagar"	ITRA	1967	https://itra.ac.in/library/
2	"Central Council for Research in Ayurvedic Sciences"	CCRAS	1969	http://www.ccras.nic.in/content/ccras-hqrs-library
3	"National Institute of Homoeopathy, Kolkata"	NIH	1975	https://www.nih.nic.in/pages/display/127-library
4	"National Institute of Ayurveda, Jaipur"	NIA	1976	https://www.nia.nic.in/library.html
5	"Central Council for Research in Homoeopathy"	CCRH	1978	https://www.ccrhindia.nic.in/index1.aspx?lsid=58&lev=1&lid=53&Regid=0&langid=1
6	"Central Council for Research in Unani Medicine"	CCRUM	1978	https://ccrum.res.in/UserView/index?mid=1514
7	"Central Council for Research in Yoga and Naturopathy"	CCRYN	1978	http://ccryn.gov.in/
8	"National Institute of Naturopathy, Pune"	NIN	1986	https://www.ninpune.ayush.gov.in/NinCMSHomepages/page?id=26
9	"Rashtriya Ayurveda Vidyapeeth-Delhi"	RAV	1988	http://www.ravdelhi.nic.in/index.html
10	"Morarji Desai National Institute of Yoga, New Delhi"	YOGAMDNIY	1998	http://www.yogamdniy.nic.in/index.aspx
11	"National Institute of Unani Medicine, Bangalore"	NIUM	2004	http://www.nium.in/library.html
12	"National Institute of Siddha, Chennai"	NISC	2005	https://nischennai.org/main/
13	"North Eastern Institute of Ayurveda and Folk Medicine Research, Pasighat"	NEIAFMR	2008	https://neiafmr.org.in/library/
14	"Central Council for Research in Siddha"	SIDDHACOUNCIL	2010	http://siddhacouncil.com/home/

15	“North Eastern Institute of Ayurveda and Homoeopathy, Shillong”	NEIAH	2012	https://neiah.nic.in/library.html
16	“All India Institute of Ayurveda, New Delhi”	AIIA	2017	https://aiia.gov.in/facilities/learning-resource-center-lrc/about-lrc/
17	“National Institute of Sowa Rigpa, Leh, Ladakh”	SOWARIGPAI NSTITUTE	2019	https://www.sowarigpainstitute.in/index.php

8. RESULTS ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

Table 2 provides information on the presence of various features related to library services on the web pages of National Institutes and Research Councils associated with AYUSH. **Basics Covered:** All libraries offer introductions, hours, and information on membership, services, collections, and staff. This ensures users have essential details for library usage. **Transparency & User Support:** AIIA, CCRAS, CCRUM, NIA, and RAV prioritize user experience by providing library rules and information on library

sections. AIIA even offers a user manual. **Mission-Driven:** CCRH, NISC, and RAV showcase a clear vision through mission/vision statements. **Staying Informed:** AIIA, CCRAS, NIA, and RAV keep users updated with new arrivals. NIA and NIH provide library usage statistics for better understanding. **Accessibility:** CCRH stands out with a dedicated section for differently-abled users. **Limited Features:** No library offers a single-window search or asks-a-librarian service (except AIIA), and ILL services are also exclusive to AIIA.

Table -2 List of National Institutes and Research Councils Providing Information on Library Websites

Sl. No.	General Information	AIIA	CCRAS	CCRH	CCRS	CCRUM	CCRYN	ITRA	YOGAMD NIY	NI A	NI H	NI N	NISC	SOWARIG PAINSTIT UTE	NIU M	NEIAF MR	NEIA H	RA V
1	Introduction	✓	✓	✓	✗	✓	✗	✗	✗	✓	✓	✓	✓	✗	✓	✗	✓	✗
2	Mission/Vision	✗	✗	✓	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✓	✗	✗	✗	✓	✗
3	Library Hours	✓	✓	✓	✗	✓	✗	✗	✗	✓	✗	✓	✓	✗	✗	✗	✓	✗
4	Library Rules	✓	✓	✓	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✓	✗	✗	✓	✗	✗	✗	✓	✗
5	Membership	✓	✓	✓	✗	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✗	✗	✗	✓	✗
6	Services	✓	✓	✓	✗	✓	✗	✗	✗	✓	✓	✗	✓	✗	✓	✗	✓	✗
7	Collection	✓	✓	✓	✗	✓	✗	✗	✗	✓	✓	✓	✓	✗	✓	✗	✓	✗
8	Infrastructure	✓	✓	✓	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✓	✗	✗	✓	✗	✗	✗	✓	✗
9	Library staff	✓	✗	✗	✗	✓	✗	✗	✗	✗	✓	✗	✓	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗
10	Library Sections	✓	✗	✓	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✓	✗	✗	✓	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗
11	Statistics	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✓	✓	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗
12	New Arrivals	✓	✗	✓	✗	✓	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗
13	Differently-abled section	✗	✗	✓	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗
14	Photocopy	✓	✗	✓	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗
Total Score		11	7	12	0	7	0	0	0	9	6	4	10	0	3	0	8	0

✓=Available ✗=Not Available

Table 3 outlines the availability of various resources and services on the library websites of National Institutes and Research Councils associated with AYUSH. **Search & Access:** Most libraries offer OPAC (online catalogue) and some provide access to e-journals and databases. **Additional Resources:** Many libraries include links to other websites, FAQs, and newspaper clippings. AIIA offers a user manual

and ILL services. **Remote Access:** CCRH, CCRUM, NIA, and RAV allow remote access to resources. AIIA, NIA, and RAV are part of consortia for wider access. DELNET is available at AIIA, CCRUM, and NISC. **Repositories:** Most libraries have repositories for institutional research. **User Support:** AIIA offers an "Ask a Librarian" service, the only one among all institutions.

Table-3 List of National Institutes and Research Councils Providing Information on Library Websites

Resources and Services	AI IA	CC RA S	CC RH	CC RS	CCR UM	CC RY N	IT R A	YOGA MDNIY	NI A	NI H	NI N	NI SC	SOWARIGPAI NSTITUTE	NI U M	NEIA FMR	NEI AH	RA V
OPAC	✓	x	✓	x	✓	x	x	x	x	✓	x	✓	x	x	x	✓	x
E-Journals	✓	x	✓	x	✓	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	✓	x	✓	x
Databases	✓	x	x	x	✓	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	✓	x	x	x
Link to other websites	✓	x	✓	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	✓	x	✓	x
FAQ's	✓	✓	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	✓	x
User manual	✓	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
Single window search	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
Ask a Librarian	✓	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
Newspaper clipping	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
SDI	✓	x	x	x	✓	x	x	x	x	✓	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
Remote access	x	x	✓	x	✓	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	✓	x
ERMD Consortia / HELINET Consortium	✓	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	✓	x	✓	x
DELNET	✓	x	x	x	✓	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
Repository	x	x	✓	x	✓	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	✓	x
ILL/document delivery	✓	x	x	x	✓	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
Total Score	12	2	6	0	9	0	0	0	1	3	1	2	0	5	0	8	0

✓=Available x=Not Available

Table 4 provides information on various features available on the library websites of National Institutes and Research Councils associated with AYUSH. **Updates & Navigation:** AIIA, CCRH, and RAV keep users informed about website updates. Only CCRH and RAV have specific features to help users navigate their sites. **User Engagement:** AIIA offers registration and feedback options. AIIA and RAV

leverage social media for engagement. **Accessibility:** AIIA and CCRAS provide downloadable forms. AIIA, NISC, NEIAH, and RAV allow keyword searches. **Limited Features:** No special layout features are mentioned. No library offers login (except AIIA) or asks-a-librarian service (except AIIA) information or resources.

Table-4: List of National Institutes and Research Councils Providing Information on Library Websites

Sl. No.	Features	AII A	CCR AS	CCR H	CC RS	CCR UM	CC RY N	IT R A	YOGAMD NIY	NI A	NI H	NI N	NI SC	SOWARIGPAI NSTITUTE	NI U M	NEIA FMR	NEI AH	RA V
1	Last update	✓	x	✓	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	✓	x
2	Navigation	x	x	✓	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	✓	x
3	Registration/ Login	✓	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	✓	x
4	Direct Link	✓	x	✓	x	✓	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	✓	x
5	Download forms	✓	✓	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
6	Social networking	✓	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	✓	x
7	Feedback	✓	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
8	Layout	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
9	Keyword Search	✓	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	✓	x	x	x	✓	x	
Total Score		7	1	3	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	6	0

✓=Available x=Not Available

Table 5 presents a comparison of various National Institutes and Research Councils based on the availability of information on their respective library websites across different categories. **Most libraries provide the basics:** General information, resources & service details are present on most websites, with a few exceptions. AIIA stands out: They offer the most

comprehensive information across all categories, including features and accessibility. The CCRYN, CCRS & NEIAFMR lack crucial details on resources & services and Features info is scarce (mainly AIIA & RAV). Accessibility details are limited (AIIA, CCRUM, NIN, NIUM & RAV). All libraries should prioritize clear information on resources & services.

Consider incorporating features like login, search enhancements, and user support

Table-5 List of National Institutes and Research Councils Providing Information on Library Websites

Sl. No.	Particulars	AI IA	CC RAS	CC RH	CC RS	CCR UM	CCR YN	IT RA	YOGAM DNIY	NI A	NI H	NI N	NI SC	SOWARIGPAI NSTITUTE	NI U M	NEIA FMR	NEI AH	R A V
1	General Information	✓	✓	✓	✗	✓	✗	✗	✗	✓	✓	✓	✓	✗	✓	✗	✓	✗
2	Resources and Services	✓	✗	✓	✗	✓	✗	✗	✗	✓	✓	✓	✓	✗	✓	✗	✓	✗
3	Features	✓	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✓	✗
4	Accessibility	✓	✗	✗	✗	✓	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✓	✗	✓	✗
Total Score		4	1	2	0	3	0	0	0	2	2	2	2	0	3	0	4	0

✓=Available ✗=Not Available

Table 6 illustrates ranking-wise library websites in the AYUSH. Top Performer: the AIIA leads the pack with a well-rounded presence across all categories (General Information, Resources & Services, Features, and Accessibility). The NEIAH offers a balanced score across most categories. The CCRH

excels in General Information but could improve Features accessibility. The CCRUM has good Resources & Services information but lacks Features. The NISC & NIA have decent information but limited Features, and the CCRAS & NIH could enhance Resources & Services and Features.

Table -6 Ranking of the AYUSH National Institute and Research Councils Library Websites

Abbreviations	General Information	Resources and Services	Features	Particulars	Total	Rank
AIIA	11	12	7	4	34	1
NEIAH	8	8	6	4	26	2
CCRH	12	6	3	2	23	3
CCRUM	7	9	1	3	20	4
NISC	10	2	1	2	15	5
NIA	9	1	0	2	12	6
CCRAS	7	2	1	1	11	7
NIH	6	3	0	2	11	8
NIUM	3	5	0	3	11	9
NIN	4	1	0	2	7	10
CCRS	0	0	0	0	0	11
CCRYN	0	0	0	0	0	12
ITRA	0	0	0	0	0	13
YOGAMDNIY	0	0	0	0	0	14
SOWARIGPA INSTITUTE	0	0	0	0	0	15
NEIAFMR	0	0	0	0	0	16
RAV	0	0	0	0	0	17

Nibbler is a free SEO audit tool for testing websites (*About Nibbler - the (Free Website Testing Tool, n.d.)*), that analyses a website's performance across various aspects. It provides a score out of 10 for categories like SEO, accessibility, and speed. Table 7 illustrates the Nibbler test-wise ranking of the websites of 17 Overall Institutes. The ranking is based on scores in five categories: Accessibility, Experience, Marketing, Technology, and Overall.

- **Overall Ranking:** SIDDHACOUNCIL (<http://siddhacouncil.com/home/>) has the highest overall score (46.1), followed by NIN (<https://www.ninpune.ayush.gov.in/>) (45.2) and AIIA (<https://aiia.gov.in/>) (43.7). CCRYN (<https://infohub.ayush.gov.in/>) (36.5) and

Table-7 Nibbler Test-wise Ranking of Overall Institutes Website

Institute	URL	Overall	Access-ibility	Exper-ience	Mark-eting	Techn-ology	Total
SIDDHACOUNCIL	http://siddhacouncil.com/home/	9.1	9.7	9.7	8.4	9.2	46.1
NIN	https://www.ninpune.ayush.gov.in/	8.7	9.6	9.4	7.8	9.7	45.2
AIIA	https://aiia.gov.in/	8.3	9.9	9.8	6.3	9.4	43.7
ITRA	https://itra.ac.in/library/	8.3	9.9	9.8	6.3	9.4	43.7
CCRAS	http://www.ccras.nic.in/	8.4	9.6	8.8	7.7	8.4	42.9
NIUM	http://www.nium.in/	8.3	9	9	7.5	8.9	42.7
NEIAFMR	https://neiafmr.org.in/	8.3	9	9	7.5	8.9	42.7
RAV	http://www.ravdelhi.nic.in/	7.8	9	9	6.1	8.5	40.4
NEIAH	https://neiah.nic.in/	7.5	8.4	7.6	6.8	7.7	38
NIA	https://www.nia.nic.in/	7.4	8.6	8.4	6.1	7.2	37.7
NIH	https://www.nih.nic.in/	7.4	8.6	8.4	6.1	7.2	37.7
NISC	https://nischennai.org/main/	7.6	9.9	7.6	4.3	8.2	37.6
CCRYN	https://infohub.ayush.gov.in/	7.3	9.2	7.7	3.6	8.7	36.5
SOWARIGPA INSTITUTE	https://www.sowarigpainstitute.in/	7.2	8.5	8	3.8	8.5	36
CCRM	https://ccrum.res.in/	7	7.8	6.9	4.5	6.7	32.9
CCRH	https://www.ccrhindia.nic.in/	6.2	7.1	7.5	5.3	6	32.1
YOGAMDNIY	http://www.yogamdniy.nic.in/	5.7	6.2	6.5	5	5.3	28.7

- **Overall:** The overall score for this website.

SOWARIGPAINSTITUTE

(<https://www.sowarigpainstitute.in/>) (36) fall in the lower range of the rankings. YOGAMDNIY (<http://www.yogamdniy.nic.in/>) has the lowest overall score (28.7).

- **Accessibility:** Most institutes score well in Accessibility, with AIIA (<https://aiia.gov.in/>) and ITRA (<https://itra.ac.in/library/>) scoring the highest (9.9). YOGAMDNIY (<http://www.yogamdniy.nic.in/>) has the lowest Accessibility score (6.2).
- **Experience:** AIIA (<https://aiia.gov.in/>) and NIUM (<http://www.nium.in/>) tie for the highest Experience score (9.8), and CCRYN (<https://infohub.ayush.gov.in/>) has a relatively low Experience score (3.6).
- **Marketing:** AIIA (<https://aiia.gov.in/>) again scores the highest in Marketing (9.8), CCRYN (<https://infohub.ayush.gov.in/>) and CCRM (<https://ccrum.res.in/>) have the lowest Marketing scores (3.6 and 4.5 respectively).
- **Technology:** CCRAS (<http://www.ccras.nic.in/>) has the highest Technology score (9.7), NISC (<https://nischennai.org/main/>) and CCRYN (<https://infohub.ayush.gov.in/>) have the lowest Technology scores (4.3 and 3.6 respectively).

- **Accessibility:** How accessible the website is to mobile and disabled users. (Includes URL format, internal links, Headings, Mobile, and Page titles).
- **Experience:** How satisfying the website is likely to be for users. (Includes URL format, Amount of content, Server behaviour, Internal links, Mobile, Images, Printability, and Freshness).
- **Marketing:** How well-marketed and popular the website is. (Includes Analytics, Meta tags, Amount of content, Internal links, Headings, Page titles, and Freshness)
- **Technology:** How well designed and built is the website? (Includes Meta tags, URL format, Server behaviour, Internal links, Headings, Mobile, Images, and Printability).

9. FINDINGS AND SUGGESTIONS

AYUSH National Institutes and Research Councils' library websites reveal significant disparities in content and accessibility. The All India Institute of Ayurveda (AIIA) provides comprehensive information, including user manuals, feedback mechanisms, and online registration. In contrast, CCRAS, CCRYN, NEIAFMR, and RAV offer minimal details, particularly regarding library features and accessibility. Most websites include basic information such as library hours, introductions, and membership details but lack essential resources like user guides, single-window search functionalities, and accessibility features.

To improve user experience, the following enhancements are recommended:

- **User Guides & Navigation Support:** Libraries should provide detailed manuals to help users access resources efficiently.
- **Single-Window & Enhanced Search:** Implementing a unified and keyword-optimized search system will improve retrieval efficiency.
- **Comprehensive & Accessible Information:** Websites should present clear, structured content with inclusive design for users with disabilities.
- **Standardization Across AYUSH Libraries:** Ensuring uniformity in content and features will create a cohesive experience.
- **By adopting these improvements, AYUSH library websites can enhance accessibility, usability, and the overall research experience**

for students and professionals in traditional medicine.

10. CONCLUSION

The analysis indicated differences in information comprehensiveness, user-friendliness, and accessibility. It identified areas for improvement, including: Standardizing the information offered on websites, Improving the user experience with features like OPAC and user manuals, and Improving accessibility features for users with varying needs. Addressing these deficiencies will allow AYUSH institutions to establish more informative and user-friendly library websites, thereby increasing research and knowledge sharing in traditional Indian medicine.

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